

IPBES BBA Chapter 1 - Setting the Scene / IPBES business and biodiversity assessment (1.1)

Code: IPBES_BBA_1.1

Versioning 02: (27.03.2025)

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12785912

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Description

A comprehensive literature review was conducted for Chapter 1 of the IPBES business and biodiversity assessment, which provides a common framework for all chapters of this assessment. The review process involved multiple approaches, including a systematic review of academic and grey literature sources, a focused institutional document analysis of IPBES assessment reports, and targeted non-systematic searches of specific bodies of literature. The aim was to identify interlinkages with existing and upcoming IPBES assessments, clarify key concepts and definitions related to biodiversity and nature, explore different business typologies, and understand the evolution of business engagement with nature by examining various impacts, dependencies, risks, opportunities, and enabling elements that support positive outcomes of business activities on biodiversity. The review also incorporated socio-cultural and Indigenous knowledge perspectives on business and biodiversity. Expert elicitation and brainstorming were used to complement the literature search. This report details the process used to complete this chapter's literature review.

In total, Chapter 1 includes 373 references identified through the literature search conducted by the authors. This number reflects the overall pool of sources integrated to support the chapter, rather than a section-by-section breakdown, as many references were relevant to multiple parts of the text. This cross-cutting use of literature highlights the integrative nature of the review, with single sources often informing several dimensions of the analysis from clarifying concepts and definitions to examining business typologies, impacts, dependencies, and enabling conditions.

Process overview

Protocol

The literature review for Chapter 1 was organized into five parts, with different experts responsible for conducting the review within their area of expertise. Findings were then synthesized and used to inform the drafting of the chapter's sections. By doing so, the chapter reflects both the range of literature and the contributions of the author team. The protocol for each part is described below:

1. Interlinkages with IPBES assessments and conceptual framework

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Focused institutional document analysis/Systematic examination of all relevant IPBES documents
- **Search languages:** English
- **Search engine:** IPBES Website (<https://www.ipbes.net/documents>)
- **Search period:** September 2023 to June 2024
- **Search terms:** N/A (filtered by document type and year)
- **Sample extracted:** 17

1.1. Detailed description of approach

A focused institutional document analysis was conducted to identify major interlinkages between existing IPBES assessments, conceptual frameworks, and related IPBES publications relevant to the business and biodiversity assessment. The process was completed in three stages.

First, the section authors systematically searched and screened the IPBES document repository by filtering documents by year and document type, including assessment reports and summaries for policymakers. The primary focus was on previous IPBES methodological assessments, thematic assessments, and related summaries for policymakers that could provide conceptual foundations for the business and biodiversity framework.

Second, each document was manually screened to assess its relevance, particularly whether it made direct reference to business and biodiversity and related concepts. In total, 17 key IPBES documents were identified and compiled for subsequent analysis (Attachment A).

Third, the documents were analysed in relation to the overarching structure of Chapter 1. Specifically, the section authors considered whether, and in what ways, previous IPBES assessments are related to the business and biodiversity methodological assessment.

2. Key definitions relevant to the business and biodiversity assessment

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Targeted but non-systematic review and expert elicitation
- **Search languages:** English
- **Search engine:** Google Scholar, Science Direct, IPBES Glossary
- **Search Period:** September 2023 to June 2024
- **Search Terms:** N/A
- **Sample extracted:** N/A

2.1. Detailed description of approach

A targeted but non-systematic literature review combined with expert elicitation was conducted to identify, define, and validate critical terms necessary for the business and biodiversity assessment.

First, section authors circulated an Excel document among selected subject-matter experts, including chapter authors and contributing lead authors, to gather initial inputs on essential terminology and concepts. Experts provided definitions, suggested alternative terms, and flagged potential ambiguities.

Second, the section authors conducted targeted literature searches using Google Scholar and Science Direct, as well as the official IPBES Glossary, to cross-reference, refine, and validate the collected definitions. Definitions were iteratively revised based on findings from the literature and through structured deliberations among authors and experts. The initial list was also circulated among other chapters for feedback, which was incorporated into the final list. The finalized definitions and key terms were used to support consistency and clarity across the assessment.

3. Searching for a ‘business’ definition for this assessment

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Systematic search, manual search, and expert elicitation
- **Search languages:** English
- **Search engine:** Web search engines (e.g., Google), websites of World Chambers Federation members
- **Exact Search Date:** March 2023
- **Search Terms:** [“business” AND (“define” OR “mean” OR “refer”)]
- **Sample extracted:** N/A

3.1. Detailed description of approach

A systematic web search was conducted in March 2023 to identify suitable definitions of the term “business,” using the Boolean search terms [“business” AND (“define” OR “mean” OR “refer”)] across general web search engines, primarily Google. This search incorporated machine learning-assisted techniques to filter and categorize results. However, it did not yield a universally applicable definition suitable for the context of this assessment.

Given these limitations, the section authors conducted a targeted manual search of websites of World Chambers Federation members, along with extensive manual review of grey literature, including reports and institutional documents, as well as academic publications.

In parallel, expert elicitation was conducted through structured discussions among the authors, contributing experts, and the Indigenous knowledge expert working group to deliberate on, synthesize, and select the most relevant definition. These deliberations focused on broader applicability, alignment with biodiversity-related discussions, and inclusivity of diverse economic models, including informal and Indigenous business practices. The selected definition of “business” served as a foundational reference for the broader assessment process.

4. Typologies of business and clarifying the difference between supply chains and value chains

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Targeted but non-systematic Literature Review
- **Search languages:** English
- **Search engine:** Google Scholar and Science Direct
- **Search Period:** September 2023 to June 2024
- **Search terms:** N/A
- **Sample extracted:** N/A
- **Summary description of approach:** N/A

4.1. Detailed description of approach

A targeted but non-systematic literature review was conducted to establish a typology of business models and clarify the conceptual distinction between supply chains and value chains.

A structured search was carried out using Google Scholar and Science Direct, focusing on academic literature on business classification frameworks, industry reports on business models, and case studies of biodiversity-linked business structures. The aim of the search was to examine distinctions between business typologies based on size, sector, and region, as well as the various classification frameworks used to categorize them.

Given the frequent misinterpretation of the terms “supply chain” and “value chain” in biodiversity-related business discussions, the section authors gave particular attention to differentiating these concepts. The objective was to clarify conceptual distinctions, identify sector-specific variations, and assess how these concepts are applied in corporate biodiversity assessments.

In parallel, structured discussions were held among authors to refine the business typology and definitions. These deliberations centred on biodiversity-related business practices, sectoral distinctions, and conceptual clarity to ensure coherence across the assessment.

The final typologies and definitions were used to support conceptual clarity and coherence across the assessment.

5. The evolution of business engagement with nature

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Targeted but non-systematic literature review, systematic examination of relevant Multilateral Environmental Agreements
- **Search languages:** English
- **Search engine:** SCOPUS and Web of Science
- **Search period:** September 2023 to June 2024
- **Search terms:** (Business OR corporate OR Private sector) AND (biodiversity OR “nature conservation”)
- **Sample extracted:** 37

5.1. Detailed description of approach

A targeted but non-systematic literature review, complemented by a systematic analysis of relevant Multilateral Environmental Agreements, was conducted to document the historical and contemporary evolution of business engagement with nature.

First, section authors carried out targeted searches in the SCOPUS and Web of Science databases using search strings such as (“business” OR “corporate” OR “private sector”) AND (“biodiversity” OR “nature conservation”). The search results were manually screened based on relevance criteria, including explicit discussion of corporate interactions with biodiversity, historical trends, documented impacts and dependencies, policy influences, and shifts in corporate practices over time.

Second, a systematic document analysis was conducted on selected Multilateral Environmental Agreements to identify the chronological progression and policy evolution of business roles in biodiversity conservation and environmental governance.

In total, a final dataset of 37 peer-reviewed academic and institutional documents was compiled for analysis (Attachment B).

Additional files

ID	Name	File Type	Size	Description
A	IPBES_BBA_1.1_03-2026_(A)	.pdf	N/A	This attachment contains the IPBES documents consulted for the analysis, including relevant IPBES assessments and conceptual framework documents.
B	IPBES_BBA_1.1_03-2026_(B)	.pdf	N/A	This attachment contains all Multilateral Environmental Agreements relevant to Business and Biodiversity and relevant reports.